

Operando TEM Studies of Re@Cu₂O-SnO₂ catalysts during CO₂ reduction reaction with optimized liquid flow configuration

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Background

The energy transition is nowadays a topic of huge attention, as a measure to face the global energy crisis and the more and more impacting climate change. In this framework, the production of carbon-based chemicals and fuels by exploiting anthropogenic CO₂ is nowadays considered a way-out to leave the traditional oil-based technology. In fact, renewable and green approaches to CO₂ valorisation are aimed at minimizing the worrying impact of its emission to the environment, and to drive the transition to a new circular economy approach in chemistry and energy production. A strategic method to reduce CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere is to consider it as a valuable raw material, collecting it from industrial point sources and electrochemically reducing it into value-added products. This green approach can contribute to the development of alternative energetic vectors, or organic molecules normally derived from fossil resources. Among many products that can be obtained, which depend on the catalyst characteristics, reaction conditions and electrolyte, the CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR) to carbon monoxide (CO) or formic acid (HCOOH) are up to now the most economically viable processes and can challenge conventional production routes [1]. In order to design efficient catalysts for CO₂RR with high activity, selectivity and stability, it is important to understand the fundamental mechanisms involved in the electrochemical processes. In this context, in situ / operando characterization techniques provide insight into the correlation between physical-chemical properties and the electrochemical performance. Specifically, electrochemical liquid phase transmission electron microscopy (EC-LPTM) yields temporally and spatially resolved morphological, structural and chemical information regarding catalytic materials under electrochemical stimulation [2]. Within this framework, in this paper, EC-LPTM experiments on molecular Re@Cu₂O/SnO₂ catalysts for CO₂RR are presented and compared to the lab-scale experiments.

Methods

EC-LPTM experiments are typically carried out in miniaturized liquid cell TEM holders with controlled liquid flow, where the electrochemical functionality may be provided with different technological approaches. Poseidon liquid phase TEM holder and related electrochemical commercial and modified chips have been used to perform EC-LPTM on a FEI TECNAI F20ST microscope.

Molecular Re@Cu₂O/SnO₂ catalysts for the CO₂ electroreduction to syngas have been prepared by wet precipitation of Cu₂O/SnO₂ followed two functionalization steps with vinyltriethoxysilane (VTES), to form stable surface Si-O bonds, with electropolymerizations on the silanized Cu₂O/SnO₂-VTES NPs with vinyl-tagged Re complex.

For the EC-LPTM, a dispersion of the catalyst in ethanol is drop casted on a Glassy Carbon working electrode in a microchip-based electrochemical set-up. This chip, together with an optimized prototype chip, provided by Protochips, are used to compose the electrochemical cell. The catalyst was studied in 0.1M KHCO₃ saturated with CO₂. The electrochemical activity for the CO₂RR was tested by means of CV and Chrono Potentiometry (CP) analyses.

Results

One major challenge in conventional liquid cell TEM setups for CO₂RR operando experiments in aqueous electrolyte is that the evolution of gaseous products at the electrodes causes the formation of gas bubbles. Due to the miniaturized volume of the liquid cell, in few seconds the cell is completely filled with gas, in electrochemical conditions which are relevant for CO₂RR. Once the cell is filled with gas, the electrolyte-electrode interface is dramatically affected, resulting in uncontrollable experimental conditions and elusive data interpretation. In this work, we use a customised liquid cell geometry with optimized liquid flow configuration, which minimizes the formation of gas bubbles in the liquid cell and concurrently removes the gaseous products more efficiently in electrochemical conditions relevant for operando CO₂RR studies in aqueous electrolyte [3], [4].

With this improved experimental capability, we investigated the morphological dynamics during the life cycle of Re@Cu₂O/SnO₂ catalysts for the CO₂ electroreduction to syngas. What emerged is that the catalyst during electrochemical activity experiences dissolution and re-crystallization phenomena, that partially change the particle size and in turn can possibly change the catalytic performance.

Conclusion

In-situ EC-LPTM helped to shed light on the changes the material undergoes during electrocatalytic activity, and thanks to improved cell we have been able to study this catalyst at relatively wide range of potentials for prolonged periods of time, which are close to those of interest for the applications. The obtained results on the catalysts hold significance from the fundamental point of view, and, in addition, the optimised design of the LP flow TEM cell allowed to perform stability tests, which are of huge interest for the future application of these catalysts in real devices.

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Keywords:

Operando EC-LPTM, CO₂RR, Cu-based catalyst

Reference:

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